

CREATIVE THERAPY FOR JUVENILE HOMICIDE OFFENDERS IN REHABILITATION CENTER

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Creative Therapy for Juvenile Homicide Offenders in Rehabilitation Center

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Abstract

This study was designed to explore and understand the common experiences of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father. It is a qualitative approach using multiple case study research design. The study was conducted to selected Shelter House of Sexually Abused Children specifically Incest case. Three (3) mothers referred by Laura Vicuña Foundation; four (4) from Palayan City Home for Girls; and three (3) mothers from NCR referred by Guidance Counselors with the case of Incest. The criteria of selection were limited to mothers whose daughter was sexually abused by their biological father. The ages of the children are between 7 and 16 years old who are still living with their mothers whose ages range from 40-59 years old. The study revealed that the experiences before, during and after the disclosure, were described as painful, unbelievable, and unexpected by the mothers. The indicative themes directly helped the mothers realize the difficulties they encountered in the arms of their own biological fathers. This represents how the indicative themes of time, person and event leads to the discovery of the abuse which leads to positive responses of being strong for their daughters as represented by the results. However, during the disclosure of the abused, it was revealed that there is an evident vision of a mother in anger and pain knowing that their daughters were abused by their biological fathers, a mother in confusion who cannot easily manage and understand the entire scene of the abuse, a mother in a jealous state since her daughter confided that in the long run of the abuse, she felt the sexual urge with his father. More so, a mother in shame is also visible for her daughter as well as her entire family because they may be put into conviction by the people around them and a mother of strength who never doubted their heart of sending her husband to jail and let him pay for his crime. Finally, the aftershock or final disclosure was also a painful revelation among daughters who were sexually abused by their own biological fathers. As such, mothers are being their daughter's shoulder to cry on, a cure to their aching hearts, a protective shield against harm, a genuine friend, and a hero to win the battle for their abused daughters. The mother and daughter respectively signify their continuous determination to move on with life and be a positive will of helping their daughters to survive from the abuse. Thus, the result became the basis in the development of a TOOLKIT FOR MOTHERS OF SEXUALLY ABUSED CHILDREN. This would be used by the guidance counselors, in helping mothers to cope up with the trauma, community and shelter house catering sexually abused children, and most specially, mothers who are the second victim of the abuse.

Keywords: *juvenile homicide offenders, aggression, empathy, prosocial behavior, creative therapy modules*

Introduction

In today's generation, committing a crime may be termed for adults and younger ones. The participation of children in different crimes is not just limited to what we call petty crimes like stealing but also in being engaged in rape, drugs, car napping, homicide, and even murder. With the fast-paced world and the demanding livelihood necessities, these young individuals adapt extensively to survive. Adults now manipulate children's behavior by being aggressive, impulsive, and curious to perpetrate crimes.

In recent data of the Regional Rehabilitation Center for Youth, Region III, under the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), as of January 15, 2019, there have been 94 children who are placed in the said center, and most of the cases fall under the violation of R.A 9165 or illegal drugs (28), rape (27) and robbery (10). Among these 94 children, there are 7 cases related to homicide. Although the data provides a small percentage of this type of criminal offense, which is similarly expressed by Vries and Liem (2011), there is urgent action to be taken in responding to their distinct and independent needs that are incomparable to other juvenile cases. This can be validated by the study conducted by De Lisi, Piquero, and Cardwell (2016) wherein they mentioned that there is minimal research that has investigated the characteristics distinguishing youth who murder other juvenile offenders. Furthermore, studies related to juvenile homicide offenders (JHOs) are limited. What we know about these extreme offenders is based only on a handful of studies, many of them with very low frequencies, often descriptive or comparing homicide offenders to other non-homicide, violent offenders (Trulson & Caudill, 2017). To support the said statement, Shumaker and Prinz (2000) claimed that despite considerable research on homicide, pre-adolescents of juvenile homicide offenders have received less attention.

As a researcher, I have been exposed to different temporary shelters and rehabilitation centers that aim to holistically help children in conflict with the law. Having been immersed while working in these centers, it came to my attention and proved the pressing insistence of the absence of intervention programs that are tailored to these children's distinct needs.

Children from these centers also expressed several sentiments and views on why others decided to escape. According to some, it is because they felt bored due to their routine activities, which mostly involve household chores and bible study. Research across the country revealed this – the necessity and earnestness to have concrete intervention protocols suitable to cater for the diverse needs of children in conflict with the law (Aguilar, 2016; Cabildo & Reysio-Cruz, 2016; Pagunuran, 2008). Although R.A 9344, or the Juvenile

Justice and Welfare Act of 2006, clearly stipulated the idea that there should be a program for rehabilitation and intervention for children in conflict with the law or CICL, several cities and local government units (LGUs) are still not aware of this provision of the law, much more of these children and the interventions that can be conducted for their reform (Aguilar, 2016; Pagunuran, 2008).

While the DSWD prides itself in being able to offer a more holistic approach to helping the said children, which includes psycho-social, educational, health care, recreational, and other cultural activities and spiritual enhancement programs (Virola, 2011), the lack of funding, insufficient number of qualified staff, and occurring inhumane and decrepit living environments that prevent these programs to fully materialize and make an impact in the lives of these children in conflict with the law persists (Cabildo & Reysio-Cruz, 2016).

Many studies are already working out on specific intervention programs to address the different types of children at risk. This may come from children who are into substance abuse (Das, Salam, Arshad, Finkelstein, & Bhutt, 2016), drug abuse (Robertson, David, & Rao, 2010) and juvenile sex offenders (Finkelhor, Ormrod, & Chaffin, 2009). Nevertheless, there is little attention given to those children who committed homicide cases (Hemenway & Solnick, 2017).

The researcher could not find a study in the local setting focusing on JHOs and intervention programs that use creative therapy specifically designed for this type of case in the country. According to Alavinezhad, Mousavi and Sohrabi (2014), using creative therapy like art therapy or play therapy (Sarpoulaki & Kolahi, 2016) is a less threatening intervention when working with children and demonstrated the effectiveness of this therapy on children with behavioral problems. Furthermore, by specific drawing tasks and questions, it would be possible to assist children in depicting their experiences to reframe negative emotions and thoughts (Malchiodi, 2003). In addition, Liebmann (2008) argued that such therapy can reach the core of the problem and deal effectively with anger. There are multiple ways of expressing anger and feelings behind anger, which uses art-based therapy and is effective for adolescents.

In this context, the researcher is motivated to develop and see the effectiveness of a creative therapy module crafted to address the needs of this type of child in conflict with the law. Accordingly, this is believed to be the research gap for this case. As Brook (2016) indicated, serious delinquents such as those committing grave assaults should be given a treatment or intervention that focuses on the causes of their behavior and attitudes that trigger offending. However, as Gerard, Jackson, Chou, Whitfield, and Browne (2014) and Heide (2003), pointed out, the lack of standardized methodologies or frameworks to understand these children hinders researchers from systematically developing interventions designed for these specific young offenders.

Research Questions

The primary aimed of the current study is to determine the effectiveness of an intervention using creative therapy modules for juvenile homicide offenders. In particular, the present study answered the following research questions:

1. How were the participants described in terms of the following behaviors before the intervention:
 - 1.1. aggression;
 - 1.1.1. physical aggression;
 - 1.1.2. verbal aggression;
 - 1.1.3. anger; and
 - 1.1.4. hostility?
 - 1.2. empathy; and
 - 1.3. prosocial behavior?
2. What are the participants' experiences during the implementation of the intervention?
3. How were the participants described in terms of the following behaviors after the intervention:
 - 3.1. aggression;
 - 3.1.1. physical aggression;
 - 3.1.2. verbal aggression;
 - 3.1.3. anger; and
 - 3.1.4. hostility?
 - 3.2. empathy; and
 - 3.3. prosocial behavior?
4. Is there a significant difference in the participants' aggression, empathy, and prosocial behavior after the intervention?

Methodology

This section presents the methods and techniques of the study, research design, site, population sample and criteria, research instrument, data collection procedure, data processing and analysis, role of researcher, methods of validation, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

A mixed method type of research, specifically embedded concurrent experimental design, was used in this research endeavor. The said design is identified using one data collection phase, during which quantitative and qualitative data are collected simultaneously (Creswell, 2015). In addition, the mixed method design has qualitative data embedded within an experimental design. The quantitative, experimental methodology and the

qualitative dataset, subservient to the methodology, establish it. Such an approach can help the researcher obtain qualitative information before and when developing an intervention or instrument (Creswell, 2009).

Figure 1: *Embedded Concurrent Experimental Model Mix Method Design*

The present study embedded the qualitative data in the quantitative analysis, a pre-experimental design. In this case, the secondary method is the qualitative part, which involves an in-depth interview. Embedded in the predominant method is the quantitative analysis, which includes the distribution of questionnaires, and the experimental method, which is the conduct of the creative therapy modules. Furthermore, the secondary data helped the study examine and validate the process of intervention and follow up on the results of the experiment since the study also involved assessment of the behaviors using standardized questionnaires before and after the conduct of the modules.

Participants

The target participants of the study are children in conflict with the law (CICL), mainly those children who committed homicide. In selecting the said participants, the inclusion criteria are as follows: 1) currently admitted to the regional rehabilitation center mentioned above; 2) committed the offense or crime within the age of 12-17 years old; 3) that remained in the center for a minimum of 1 month. Also, the researcher interviewed the center's house parents, social workers, and resident psychology case workers for additional data. The said key persons were considered process observers since they provided more valid insights, considering that they could witness the status and situation of the target participants. Their responses and observations were used to validate the participants' responses and experiences gained after the therapy was conducted.

Since the target participants are few due to the rareness of the case, the researcher utilized a small n design, specifically the A-B-A approach that involves the process of measuring, offering, and withdrawing treatment (Graham, Karmarkar, & Ottenbacher, 2012). Measuring or the first 'A' is considered the baseline data. In the case of the present study, the participants took the standardized questionnaires that measured their behaviors, including their level of aggression, empathy, and prosocial behavior, before providing them with the intervention, and creative therapy modules. In addition, statements and observed behaviors of the center personnel to the participants were included as baseline data. When it comes to the offering, denoted as B, this involves the intervention wherein, in the case of the present study, it is the creative therapy modules. Lastly, the withdrawal of treatment symbolizes the last A or the post-measurement of the behaviors using standardized questionnaires. Another set of information from the center personnel concerning the observed behaviors of the participants also supported this. One of the considerations of the small 'n' is that participants will be treated as individuals, not as a group (Graham, et al., 2012).

When it comes to the exclusion criteria, those participants who stayed less than a month in the center were not included even if they were considered children with homicide cases. In addition, center personnel with no background of the participants from the very start of their admission were also excluded. The final number of participants was reduced to six (6). This was because one of them escaped due to an untoward incident. This participant ran and could not complete the sessions through creative therapy modules.

Instruments

The study used three (3) different standardized questionnaires to measure the participants' aggression, hostility, empathy, and prosocial behaviors.

First, the Aggression Questionnaire (AQ) was developed by Buss and Perry (1992). It is a 29-item with 5 point Likert scale ranging from 1-as extremely uncharacteristic of me to 5-as extremely characteristic of me. The tool obtained a strong coefficient alpha or internal consistency which is .80. AQ/has four (4) factors that individually describe the aggression being experienced by an adolescent. The first factor is Physical Aggression, which is composed of 9 items. This measures the tendency to use physical force when expressing anger or aggression. It was also found to have a strong internal consistency (.80). Another factor is verbal aggression, which assesses the tendency to be verbally argumentative. The said factor was composed of 5 items and yielded .76 internal consistencies. The third factor is Anger, which measures anger-related arousal and sense of control. It has 7 items with a reliability coefficient of .72. The fourth and final factor of aggression is Hostility, with 8 items. It measures the feelings of resentment, suspicion, and alienation or the emotions

that seriously undermine physical and psychological health. When it comes to its reliability, hostility obtained a .72 coefficient alpha. Furthermore, Asian countries like Iftikhar and Malik's (2014) study used AQ and even translated it into their language. The author's permission to use this questionnaire was secured.

When measuring the participants' empathy construct, the researcher used the Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI) by Davis (1980). It is a 28-item questionnaire answered on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "0 (A)=does not describe me well" to "4(E)=describe me very well". The said instrument has four (4) subscales, each made up of 7 different items. The subscale is perspective taking, which tends to adopt the psychological point of view of others spontaneously. The said subscale obtained an alpha coefficient of .78. Another subscale is the Fantasy scale, which was recorded to have a coefficient alpha of .75. This subscale taps the individual's tendency to transpose themselves imaginatively into the feelings and actions of fictitious characters in book, movies, and plays. The third subscale is termed the Empathic Concern scale, which assesses "other-oriented" feelings of sympathy and concern for unfortunate others. In addition, it is used to measure an individual's compassionate emotional response to those in distress (Varker & Devilly, 2007). This subscale was recorded to have a coefficient alpha score of .72. The last subscale is the Personal Distress scale. This subscale yielded a .78 alpha coefficient and measured "self-oriented" feelings of personal anxiety and unease in tense interpersonal settings. Multiple studies in other parts of Asia could translate and utilize the IRI (Huang, Li, Sun, Chen, & Davis, 2012; Nomura & Akai, 2012; Siu & Shek, 2005).

Although the tool comprises 4 subscales, the current study utilized only the subscale Emphatic Concern to measure the behaviors of empathy. Furthermore, multiple researchers (Hawk, Keijsers, Branje, Graaff, Wied, & Meeus, 2014; Oberle, Schonert-Reichl, & Thomson, 2010; Verschuere, Candel, Van Reenen, & Korebrits, 2012) have already made use in their respective scholarly studies of the same subscale from the IRI with the adolescent population.

Meanwhile, the IRI (Davis, 1980) is a free and public-domain instrument that does not require permission from the author to use in the research (Barton, 2016). Still, the author's approval was secured to use the questionnaire.

The last scale used to assess the participants' prosocial behavior level is the Self-Report Aggression and Social Behavior Measure (SRASBM) developed by Morales and Crick (1998). It is a 56-item self-report instrument with a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (not at all true) to 7 (very true) assigned to assess various social behaviors in older adolescents. It consists of six subscales, namely, relational aggression, physical aggression, relational victimization, physical victimization, exclusivity, and prosocial behavior. Cronbach alpha for the various subscales of the SRASBM has been reported as ranging from .71 to .87 by multiple studies that used the said scale (Bailey & Ostrov, 2008; Goldstein et al., 2008; Lento-Zwolinski, 2007; Linder et al., 2002; Miller & Lyman, 2003; Murray-Close et al. 2010; Ostrov & Houston, 2008; Schad et al.2008). The SRASBM's applicability has already been tested in Asian countries like Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, and Iran (Woike, 2016).

For the study, the researcher only used the subscale Prosocial Behavior, which consists of 11 items, to assess the said construct of the participants. The reliability of the said subscale was tested on individuals ages 13 to 18 years old and found reliability ranging from .90 to .93 by recent studies (Hawk et al., 2013; Clark, Dahlen, & Nicholson, 2015). Like the AQ and IRI, SRASBM was considered a free tool to use for research purposes as long as the author is given credit by citing it properly (Bryant, 2017). Likewise, the researcher was granted permission to use and translate the tool.

The researcher also considered possible issues with the language barrier. Considering that the participants may lack vocabulary skills, which might have prevented them from answering the questionnaires properly, the researcher translated the said items/subscales into Filipino to be able to lessen the probability of having problems when answering the questionnaires.

Two (2) Filipino majors, who had both positions as head teachers in their respective institutions, translated the questionnaires. After this, the researcher subjected the questionnaires through pilot testing participated by 150 individuals ages 15-18. The Aggression Questionnaire, which consists of 29 items, yielded a Cronbach alpha of .76. In contrast, the Interpersonal Reactivity Index, specifically the domain of empathy, which composed of 7 items, incurred an alpha coefficient of .70. Lastly, the domain Prosocial Behavior which consists of 11 items from the questionnaire Self-Report of Aggression and Social Behavior Measure obtained the highest Cronbachs alpha of .93. These results permitted the participants to use the questionnaires since it yielded an acceptable to excellent internal consistency. According to Tavokol and Dennick (2011), Cronbach's alpha ranges from .7 and above and is considered acceptable to excellent internal consistency.

Procedure

Communication letters were sent to the concerned department that is handling the operation of the target rehabilitation center. This was done to seek permission to conduct the said study. After rigorous review and meetings with the department heads, permission was granted to the researcher. This was followed by meeting the target participants in groups and individuals to provide them with a letter of introduction explaining the study's purpose and seeking their permission to be part of the present study.

All the participants agreed to participate voluntarily and could sign the consent forms in front of their center personnel. Moreover, the participants were informed regarding the confidentiality of the undertaking to ensure that they were impartial or provided their responses without reservation. An opportunity to withdraw from the study was also pointed out in case they felt uncomfortable and

threatened as the procedure transpired. In addition, participants also agreed to use a voice recorder during the entire course of the study for validation purposes. In addition, informed consent includes all the information the participants need to know regarding the study.

The center personnel comprises social workers, house parents, and psychology case workers. They were also given letters of invitation to participate in the study and informed consent for their voluntary participation.

Before developing the modules, the researcher interviewed in a temporary shelter catering to juveniles with the same case as the target participants. Relevant information and observations about these juveniles, as well as literature and studies supporting the information gathered, were used to craft the modules addressing the behaviors: aggression, empathy and pro-social behavior.

The data gathering was done for 3 months and comprised 16 sessions. It has 3 phases: pre-intervention, proper and post-intervention. This provides an explicit and systematic conduct of the said interventions.

Phase 1: Pre-Intervention

The researcher administered three (3) questionnaires to evaluate their aggression, empathy and prosocial behavior. An aggression Questionnaire (AQ) was used to measure their aggressive tendencies, while participants' level of empathy was measured using the subscale empathic concern of Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI). Furthermore, the researcher used the subscale Prosocial Behavior of the Self-Report Aggression and Social Behavior Measure (SRASBM) when assessing the participants' prosocial behaviour. After the pre-assessment of the said behaviors, the researcher interviewed the participants, focusing on their cases and behaviors before and during their admission to the center. To validate the information from the participants, the researcher also interviewed their assigned center personnel, such as social workers, psychology case workers, and house parents, who were later considered process observers. All the observations and information relevant to the participants' behavior were used to validate the results of their assessment of the said behaviors.

Phase 2: Intervention Proper

Regarding the interventions, creative therapy modules were conducted for a specific time allotted per participant. It was conducted individually since the participants are only 6 in number, and it is one of the protocols and considerations included when utilizing small n or participants with critical cases.

The first module processed the aggressive behavior of the participants is entitled "Slowly but Surely". Part of the objectives of this module is to help the participant learn appropriate anger management by using visualization, which can later result in becoming aware of how others may be affected by their behavior when they are angry. The module used creative arts like balloons to help the facilitator demonstrate the activity to the participants.

The second creative therapy module is entitled "Secret Heart". This module helped the participants process their covert feelings about their positive and negative behaviors. It helped them recognize the good things that they have in their hearts and process them with the help of a resident with whom he is not familiar.

Lastly, another creative therapy module entitled "Faith in Humanity" was conducted as part of the intervention for the participants. This creative therapy is a form of cinema therapy demonstrating prosocial acts and behavior. The said video was used to connect with the participants regarding their potential and ability to show concern and do good things for others. Moreover, an interview was embedded during the processing of the creative therapy modules, which targets their experiences during the therapy. It facilitated reach information in connection with the concerned behaviors.

Phase 3: Post Intervention

After providing each participant with an intervention addressing the said behaviors, post-measure commences. The said behaviours were assessed after all the creative therapy modules were conducted. In addition, another interview session was conducted with the process observers or center personnel focusing on what they observed in the participants' behaviors after the conduct of creative therapy modules. On the other hand, the participants were once again interviewed after the modules dealing with their changed and improved behaviors brought about by the therapy were conducted.

All interviews, administration of questionnaires and intervention programs were conducted in the specified rehabilitation center for them to feel secure and comfortable.

Data Analysis

To assess the participants' aggression, empathy and prosocial behavior, the researcher used descriptive statistics, specifically frequency and mean, which provides simple summaries about the sample and data being measured. In addition, the researcher utilized inferential statistics, specifically paired sample t-test, to analyze the significant difference between the measured behavior before and after the creative therapy modules.

Meanwhile, thematic analysis was employed to analyze the participants' answers during the in-depth interview. As proposed by Clarke and Braun (2014), thematic analysis is a method for identifying and interpreting patterns of meaning across qualitative data. This

approach involves a six-phase process. First is familiarizing yourself with the data and identifying items of potential interest. This phase consists of reading and re-reading the data to become immersed and intimately familiar with its content. The second phase is generating initial codes. This phase involves developing succinct labels or codes identifying essential data features relevant to answering the research question. In addition, it involves coding the entire dataset and then collating all the codes and all the relevant data extracts together or at a later stage of analysis. The third is searching for themes. This phase comprises examining the codes and collated data to identify significantly broader patterns of meaning. Then, it implicates collating data relevant to each candidate theme so that it can work the data and review the viability of each candidate theme. Fourth is reviewing potential themes. This part is related to checking the candidate themes against the dataset to determine that they tell a convincing story of the data and one that answers the research question. In this phase, themes are typically refined, which sometimes involves them being split, combined or discarded. The fifth phase of thematic analysis is defining and naming themes. This phase involves developing a detailed analysis of each theme, working out the scope and focus on each theme, and determining each story. It also takes deciding on an informative name for each theme and producing the report. This is the part where the analytic narrative and data extracted are weaved together, and the analyses with existing literature are contextualized; as Clarke and Braun (2014) indicated, overall, thematic analysis provides an accessible, flexible, foundational method for qualitative data analysis, with clear guidelines for conducting analysis. Furthermore, it offers comparatively easy qualitative research and can be used to answer many research questions.

Ethical Considerations

Communication letters that sought permission for this present study were addressed to the director of the concerned agency or department handling the said rehabilitation center. The department already responded to the letter and was asked to present the study findings in their regional research unit.

Ethical considerations were observed throughout this research study. Participants were informed on all aspects of the research that might influence their willingness to participate, namely, the purpose of the study, data collection, and feedback on the results. All the needed information regarding the proposed study were indicated in the informed consent and in the invitation letter to the center personnel. This ensured the transparency of the research and the process the participants went through during the entire study.

Before the data-gathering phase, all participants' written and signed consent, including their house parents, social workers and psychology case workers, were secured.

According to the article written by McMillan and Schumacher (2006), the well-being of research participants must be the top priority whenever research is conducted on people. This principle must not be dismissed as irrelevant, or we can find ourselves making decisions that eventually bring us to the point where our study threatens to disrupt the lives of the people under study. Participants in this research were ensured of their confidentiality, anonymity and avoidance of physical psychological harm. This was addressed by allowing them to withdraw anytime they wanted when they felt uncomfortable during the study. Through such, participants received necessary interventions, like counseling.

The researcher did not specify their names in a given response to ensure anonymity. Instead, pseudonyms were used to protect their identity. Furthermore, the reporting of data was done in individual and general forms. However, the institution's name has been mentioned in the research proposal since the permission was granted.

All data sources, like the transcripts and recorded audio during the study, were kept in a storage box that the researcher could access. No cases of uncontrolled behavior of the participants were observed during the study.

Since the study requires ample time and emotional exertion, the researcher provided food and refreshments at every meeting with the participants and center personnel. It was also used to motivate them and positively participate during the entire course of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the results appertaining to the pre-interview and assessment of the participants focusing on aggression, empathy and prosocial behavior, before the creative therapy modules, as well as the results after facilitating the said modules. In addition, center personnel who are considered process observers are composed of house parents (HP), registered social workers (RSW), and psychology case workers (PCW) provide their insights and observations on the behaviors of the participants, which were used to validate and support the quantitative results and experiences of the participants during the conduct of the modules.

Pre-Assessment Phase: Administration of Questionnaires and Interviews prior to the conduct of Creative Therapy Modules

Table 1 contains the data that address the first research problem: How did the participants described their aggression, empathy and prosocial behavior before the creative therapy modules.

Table 1 presents the participants' level of aggression and its domains before the conduct of the modules. Focusing on the aggression construct, it displays that all the domains of aggression, which include physical aggression (4.15), verbal aggression (4.20), anger (4.04), and hostility (3.88), yielded a high score and have an overall verbal description of high level (4.07). Since the participants scored high on aggression, the chances of hurting someone and their capability of posting arguments, which may result in physicality, are

evident. Similarly, Llorca-Mestre et al. (2017) found that physical and verbal aggressive behaviors were significantly higher in JHOs compared to non-JHOs.

Table 1. *The participants level of Aggression before the conduct of the Modules*

Verbal Interpretation	Physical Aggression				Verbal Aggression				Anger				Hostility				Overall Aggression			
	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD
High (3.34 – Above)	6	100			6	100			6	100			6	100			6	100		
Average (1.67 – 3.33)	0	0.00	4.15	0.64	0	0.00	4.20	0.25	0	0.00	4.04	0.42	0	0.00	3.88	0.48	0	0.00	4.07	0.16
Low (1.66 – Below)	0	0.00			0	0.00			0	0.00			0	0.00			0	0.00		

These juveniles already manifested aggressive tendencies even before being admitted to the center. In the study, being aggressive indicates that the participants have violent tendencies like subtle fistfights, verbal arguments, serious threats or harm, injuring somebody, and even destroying things.

These were their accounts during an interview before the modules were conducted. It is quite evident that aggressive acts and behavior existed even before the incident or the case happened. The statements below are some of the evidence concerning aggression:

“Jeremy: ahh pag may nakita po na nakorsonadahan, yun minsan bigla nalang sasapikin nalang po ganun. Para maghanap ka, ay kukuha ka ng paraan para lang mag pang abot kayo.”

“Ahh when I see someone, I just impulsively hit that random person. In order for you to engaged in a fight, you’ll do everything to trigger or provoke the other person.”

“Ron: Sabi ko ano, To, tara ano, nasubukan mo nabang pumatay ng tao? niloko ko lang po talaga siya nun. Ta’s sinaksak ko po sa leeg.”

“I asked him if he has killed someone, but it was just a joke. Then I stabbed her in the neck.”

“Tolits: napapaaway din po. Mga suntukan po ganun.”

“I’m also engaged in fights like brawl.”

Corroborating the findings with empirical studies and literature, late research conducted by Darby, Allan, Kashani, Hartke, and Reid (1998) discovered that most of the JHOs had previously committed a variety of conduct problems or status offenses, as well as the history of aggressive behaviors. The said findings matched the study of DiCataldo and Everett (2008), wherein they cited that these juveniles had a delinquency history before their committed case. In addition, these juveniles have identified themselves as having problems with anger. Likewise, in Dahlberg’s (2000) study, a history of early aggression is one of the strongest predictors of later aggression and criminal involvement.

In relation to this, since all the participants in this study are males, Vries and Liem (2011) have found that male JHOs were seen to have a lack of self-control and high chances of doing the same incident they committed. This is true in the study of Kremen (2018), that one of the risk factors in committing an offense or crime is a lack of self-control behaviors.

Another way to show their aggressiveness is by doing or performing violent or hostile behaviors. They were also observed performing aggressive acts while serving their rehabilitation program in the center. Below are some of the process observer’s or the center personnel’s notes on these juveniles’ involvement in aggressive behaviors inside the center:

“RSW: ahhh meron pa. actually, may dalawa pa nakarating sa ken na case dati. Ano dalawang incident ng suntukan. Ang investigation ano, nangyari sa loob ng kwarto. Parang nasulsulan siya.”

“Ahh there are actually 2 cases that I received, both fistfights. With my investigation, it happened inside their room. It appeared that he was provoked.”

“HP: Pero makikita mo talaga yan sa mukha niya ano, yung galit na galit. Kung hindi ako nag kakamali yung pangalawang away niya ano dahil mahaba kuko nya, yung nakalmut niya yung isa sa pisngi.”

“You will see on his face that he was furious. If I’m not mistaken in the second brawl he got into, he scratched the face another, his nails were long.”

Such exposure to aggressive behaviors, even inside a facility, can increase the tendency for the offender to repeat his case, as proven by other studies. It has been said that factors related to the recidivism of juvenile homicide offenders have included engaging in assaultive behavior while confined, a shorter length of time served, and measurements of negative behavior in the first few months of assessment (Caudill & Trulson, 2016; Trulson & Caudill, 2017).

The observations are parallel to their quantitative results during their pre-test scores under the said behavioral construct, wherein all the participants obtained a high level of aggression. It clearly illustrates that these juveniles show aggressive and delinquent tendencies before and even while receiving their rehabilitation program.

In addition, JHOs, as well as murder cases, were also identified to be more aggressive compared to non-homicide or murder cases. Their resident psychology case worker (PCW) verbatim stated that:

“PCW: ahh oo sir. aggressive talaga yan lalo na pag napuno mo. Yung na provoke. Hindi ka nila bibiruin talaga. Yun, yong yung mga difference nila sa iba. Kung бага malayo talaga malayo sa iba.”

(“Ahh yes Sir. He’s really aggressive especially when he had enough of you. They would really take you seriously. That makes them different from others. They’re really far from others.”)

These observations were found to be related to the study of Llorca-Mestre et al. (2017), wherein their team found that JHO’s aggressive tendencies are much higher as compared to those who are in non-homicide cases.

Another component that may lead to aggression is their tendency to become superior to others. According to the center personnel, participants seemingly have established authority inside the center. Their directing figure sets them apart from other CICLs. Such unique observation is linked to their previous case and their aggressive tendencies. Other residents are fearsome, which leads them to follow others to these juveniles. As their PCW confessed:

“PCW: Dun naman sa isang banda sir, is yung iba takot so ang tendency e sumusunod sila sa mga yan. Parang ano mataas yung leeg, yung hindi talaga sila papalag sakanila ganun.”

(“On the counterpart Sir, other people obey them out of fear, as if they are left with no other option but to follow.”)

“PCW: Ewan ko kung ano, pero siguru ano yung dahil mas mabigat yung case nila, kaya siguro nagkakaroon ng superiority”

(“I really don’t know, but maybe because of their serious cases, they became superior.”)

Not only their co-resident has this impression, but also their HPs who are very vocal about this:

“HP: tapos minsan may pagkatapang yan dito kasi sir yung pag gusto niya siya nasusunod.”

(“Sometimes he acts superior and becomes imposing.”)

“HP: Nag leleader leader din naman dati sakanila.”

(“He’s acting like a leader here.”)

“HP: Mayor mayor din kasi yan sa kwarto nila”

(“He’s the big boss in their room.”)

This behavior can be supported by the findings of a late study (Shumaker & Prinz, 2000) that claims that juvenile homicide offenders’ aggressive tendencies may come from a sense of control over impulse and the ability to formulate alternative solutions when facing difficult situations.

Given that these juveniles are aggressive and authoritative at the same time, they are still observed to be influenced by others. Some participants involved themselves in different aggressive acts and behaviors while inside the center due to their co-residents influence. Below are some of the verbatim statements by their center personnel:

“HP: Yung ano kasi sir madaling mauto. Yung papagawa sa kanya gagawin niya. kasi yung sabi saken siya daw sumapak dun sa kaaway nila ganun.”

(“He can easily be swayed. He’ll do whatever they’ll ask him to do, Because I was told that he was the one who punched their enemy.”)

“RSW: Yung parang ano sir, nakikibagay siya. kaya ano din, ganun din siya siguru nahahawa. Yung parang ano yung parang pag sinabi gagawin ganun. Pero okay naman yan masunurin siya”

(“Maybe he wants to belong that’s why he tends to be like them –whatever is asked him to do he obeys. But he is okay, he follows orders.”)

Supporting the claim, Farris and Ennett (2012) asserted that both aggressive behavior and the status of valuation of friends increase an adolescent’s likelihood of aggression. This result is relatively similar to Christakis and Fowler (2007), and Steglich, Snijders, and Pearson (2007) found that peer influence significantly increases the aggressive behaviors of their friends and peers.

Table 2. Participants level of Empathy before the conduct of the Modules

Verbal Interpretation	f	%	Mean	SD
High (15 – Above)	0	0.00	13.00	1.10
Low (14 – Below)	6	100.00		

n=6

Table 2 shows that the participants obtained a low level of empathy. Such a result can be attributed to their tendency to become hotheaded and ill-tempered. In addition, some of the participants brutally committed their offenses without reservations. Below are

some of the statements of the participants concerning the said results:

“Jeremy: ahh sa sobrang init po ng ulo ko, kwan po ano may nadisgrasya po ako. Naka patay.”
 (“Ahh with the outburst of my temper, I accidentally killed someone.”)

“Joselito: siguro po dahil din po saken. Pag ka maitin po ng ulo.”
 (“Maybe it was also because of me. I have a bad temper”)

“Ron: kwan po. Ano ahhh sinaksak ko po sa leeg. Tapos si ano po tinali niya para hindi maka galaw.”
 (“It’s... Ahhh, I stabbed him in the neck. And then, someone tied him so he wouldn’t move.”)

Blair (2018) highlighted the connection between empathy and aggression. Emotional expressions like low empathy may result in increased anger, both associated with maladaptive aggression. Multiple studies (Calley & Gerber, 2008; Carrera, Oceja, Caballero, Muñoz, López-Pérez, & Ambrona., 2013; Olthof, 2012; Ottoni Wilhelm & Bekkers, 2010; Texas Juvenile Justice Department, 2011; Wagaman, 2011) have already attested that lack of empathy is directly associated with delinquent acts and behaviors and other serious offense.

Furthermore, Vochon et al. (2013) stated that empathy plays a vital role in the aggressive behaviors of an individual. Accordingly, conduct disorders, antisocial disorders and other externalizing syndromes related to aggression are all characterized by low empathy, which can be found in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders 5th Edition. In addition, Kermen (2018) found that a lack of empathy in children is associated with crime.

Meanwhile, Llorca-Mestre et al. (2017) study regarding prosocial reasoning and emotions in young offenders and non-offenders, their results states that male JHOs were found to have a lower empathic concern as compared to those female JHOs. This is related to the current findings of the study, considering that all the participants are males and their overall level of empathy falls under the low category.

Table 3. *Participants level of Prosocial Behavior before the conduct of the Modules*

<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
High (4.68 – Above)	2	33.34		
Average (2.34 – 4.67)	4	66.66	4.23	2.17
Low (2.33 - Below)	0	0.00		

n=6

Nevertheless, despite having a low level of empathy and a high level of aggression, the participants still performed certain behaviors that depicted helping others and becoming more responsible youths inside the center. Table 3 shows that the participants obtained an average level of prosocial behavior. These results can be validated by some of the observations from the center personnel which focused on being obedient, cooperating, helping others, and volunteering, as well as trying to comply with the rules and regulations set by the center.

“HP: saka ano nauutusan yan kahit sinong social worker. Kahit sa mga dad and mom niya sumusunod yan.”
 (“He complies to all of the social workers. He’s obedient even to the Dads and Moms (house parents).”)

“HP: Nauutusan mo yan. Tatapusin niya yung pinapagawa mo.”
 (“You can give him orders. He would finish what he is being asked to do.”)

“RSW: Pero masipag naman kasi gusto nya lagi ginagawa. Kaya ngayon naka duty siya sa kitchen. Yun saka gusto nya nag gagarden garden din.”

(“But he is industrious because he enjoys doing chores. That is why he is now on duty in the kitchen. He likes to do gardening as well.”)

Although participants scored low under empathic concern before the conduct of the modules, knowing that they have this tendency to help others, their obedience could be a good sign to start establishing their empathy. In an article written by Jackson (2017), he reiterated that the essence of obedience consists of the fact that a person comes to view themselves as an instrument for carrying out another person’s wishes who are already considered responsible for their actions.

Meanwhile, the said descriptions of prosocial behavior are somehow related to the study of Hammond, Waugh, Satlof-Bedrick, and Brownel (2015), that children’s prosocial behaviors include acts such as sharing, helping, comforting, and cooperating and even come to involve complex behaviors such as lying to protect someone’s feelings. In the study, some of the participants express the way how they can promote prosocial behaviors:

“Jeremy: ahh kina dad po ano, yung kwan, sumusunod sa utos nila. Yung sa kitchen, kina mom, saka ano po, yung sa gate pag pinapasara.”

(“Ahh with Dad, I’m following their orders. Also in the kitchen with Mom and when they ask me to close the gate.”)

“Vincent: Sumusunod po minsan po pag tapos po ng pinapagawa po nila dito nag wawalis po. Misan po nagpapamiryenda po sila.”
 (“I sometimes follow what they asked me to do. Sometimes when I’m done sweeping they give us snacks.”)

“Mario: ayun po, ano, sinusunod ko po utos nila dad romell at nanay. Kasi para po naming sila magulang dito.”

(“I obey Dad Rommel and nanay because they are like our parents here.”)

Meanwhile, supporting the tendency of the participants to show concerns that would benefit others, it is a given fact, according to Dunfield (2014), that prosocial behavior occurs when a negative state is present than when it is absent. In the case of the participants, the negative state is their current condition, which entails them to comply with the center's rules and perform the task given to them. This prompted them to follow what is mandated by the center and avoid doing things that may cause trouble or problem to others.

Furthermore, center personnel shared their thoughts concerning these juveniles' tendency to follow orders. The goal of the center's diversion program is to off-lead the participants from their perceptions and ideals of their past experiences by following rules and regulations as mandated by the center. According to their PCW, all juveniles must obey all the instructions given to them since this could help them establish their identity inside the center and later be included in their progress report. Accordingly:

“PCW: Ano kasi sir, dito sa center kasi lahat ng bata eh kailangan sumunod ganun. parang kunyari pag inutusan mo. Susunod dapat. Kasi naniniwala sila na makaka rating yun sa judge kapag nag hearing sila. Kung baga plus points ganun”

(“Here in the center sir, all of them are required to follow the rules set by the center. Because they believe that the judge may give them merits once they follow the rules.”)

Intervention Phase: Conduct of the Creative Therapy Modules

Regarding the second research question, table 4 would answer the problem: what are the participants' experiences while implementing the creative therapy modules.

Table 4. Participants' experiences during the conduct of the Modules

Themes	Definition	Sample Statements
REFLECTIVE	It is how the participants understand his actions and their consequences.	<p>“Ron: ahh e yung sinabihan po kami ni Dad Jerry, kahit anong mangyari kahit iniwan pa kayo ng magulang niyo, nanay niyo pa din yan. Tapos sabi ko kay ate ko na, ate sana intindihin mo na lang, kahit iniwan tayo nanay pa din natin yan. At saka hindi nga po natitiis ng magulang yung anak”</p> <p>(“Ahh, when Dad Jerry told us that whatever happens, even if your mother has abandoned you, she is still your mother. And then, I told my sister, I hope you'll just try to understand that she is still our mother. And that, a parent cannot bear abandoning her child.”)</p> <p>“Vincent: oyo dad. Mahirap po dito yung buhay. Saka baka po ano sa jail na po ako mapunta hindi na dito kapag ano po, dad, naulit.”</p> <p>(“Yes, Dad. The life here is difficult. Then, I might go into the jail if I repeated the same action.”)</p> <p>“Mario: Yung nagawa ko po. Hindi po ano sila ma punta sa ganito. E napakahirap po ng ganito lalo na po sa city jail.”</p> <p>(“With what I have done, I hope that they won't be placed in this situation as because it is very difficult especially being in the city jail.”)</p>
CONSCIOUS	It refers to being aware and sensible of their wrongdoings and how these may affect their social identity.	<p>“Jeremy: Tska po kasi ano, parang pag napakita ko yun parang wala nang lalapit sa akin”</p> <p>(“I I reveal that truth about me, nobody would come near me.”)</p> <p>“Ron: e ano po kasi yung naka disgrasya ako, yung nakasaksak, baka po kasi pag-usapan ako yung hindi po ako lapitan.”</p> <p>(“Ahmm... My having accidentally stabbed and killed someone might be a reason for them to avoid me.”)</p> <p>“Ron: Hmm. Ano po kasi sir. ahhh kasi po hindi ako makahalubilu dito kasi po ano nahihiya ako sa kaso ko. kasi ano po ano eh, baka lumayo sila pag nalaman nila yung nagawa ko.”</p> <p>(“Hmm, I cannot mingle with them for I am ashamed of my case. They would probably stay away from me, once they find out what I've done.”)</p> <p>“Tolits: kinokontrol ko po kasi dito yung galit ko. hindi na po. Ayaw kuna pong bumalik dito. Hehe.”</p> <p>(“I am controlling my anger here because I don't like to be back here, hehe.”)</p>
COMPOSED	It refers to the participants' behavior, feelings and expressions in dealing with negative emotions.	<p>“Vincent: Kasi po hangat kaya ko naman pong intindihin sila ganun po para din po umiwas na din po sa gulo dito po. Para hindi na po mapaaway.”</p> <p>(“I would try to understand them so that I could avoid being into fight again.”)</p>

		<p>“Mario: ahh yun nga po, ano po, na dapat hindi po nagpapadala kaagad sa ano po, sa away. <i>Kasi tayo din po nakakaawa pagka ano po, nangyari yung may nasaktan kang iba.</i>” (“Ahh that is it one should not be hooked into a fight. Because it would be a pity having hurt someone.”)</p> <p>“Jeremy: <i>Ahh bali pag ano po galit ka ganyan, wag na pong patulan o ilabas po agada gad.ano nalang po lumayo nalang</i>” (“When you are angry do not react impulsively. Just walk away.”)</p>
COMPASSIONATE	It refers to how the participants express their genuine concern to others.	<p>“Vincent: <i>minsang pag kailangan po nila ng tulong, kahit hindi na po sila hihingi ng tulong magkukusa na po ako. Kunyari po pag nagbubuhay po sila ng lamesa upuan ganyan</i>” (“Sometimes when they need help, I am showing my initiative in helping them even though they don't ask for it. Example, when they would carry table, chairs, and like.”)</p> <p>“Joselito: <i>pagka my problema po yung kaibigan po, handa ko po silang pakinang. Basta po e kaya ko po naman e tutulong naman po ako</i>” (“When my friends have a problem, I'm willing to listen. As long as I can, I am really willing to help.”)</p> <p>“Ron: <i>ahh binibigyan ko din po sila ng pagkain. Pag wala po ng makain yung sa mga labas nung nasa labas pa po ako ganun.</i>” (“Ahh, when I was still out of the center, I would do the same, giving food to the hungry.”)</p>
GRATEFUL	It refers to how the participants recognize the help brought to them by sharing their thoughts and feelings with others.	<p>“Vincent: <i>magaan po sa pakiramdam dad. kasi po nalalabas ko po yung tinatago ko po. Katulad nga po nung mga barkada ko</i>” (“It was a fulfilling feeling, Dad, because I have expressed what I have kept inside, just like with my peer group.”)</p> <p>“Jeremy: <i>ahh opo, yung at least nasabi ko na po, medyo magaan po sa pakiramdam.</i>” (“Ahh yes, at least I have expressed it already. I felt better.”)</p> <p>“Tolits: <i>masaya po. Naibahagi ko po sa kanya.</i>” (“I am happy. I was able to express it to him.”)</p>
FAITHFUL	It refers to the participants' strong spiritual faith and uses it as a motivation to become a better individual.	<p>“Ron: <i>sa sarili po. Saka manalig lang po sa taas.. ahh kasi po yung diyos lang naman po yung ano, yung may Karapatan na humusga. Ganun po.</i>” (“For me, to keep the faith for God for He is the only one who could judge us.”)</p> <p>“Tolits: <i>hihikayatin ko po sila na ano, yung mag simba maniwala sa diyos para maiwas sa gulo. Para po ano hindi sila gumaya sa akin po ganun.</i>” (“I would encourage them to go to church and have faith in God in order to avoid being involved in fight and for them not to be like me.”)</p> <p>“Jeremy: <i>Gusto kong ipakita na may diyos ako. kahit gusto ko po kahit, yung magbago na po yung tingin nila sa akin.</i>” (“I would like to show that I have God and change the way other people see me.”)</p>
OBEDIENT	It is the characteristics of the participants to be good followers.	<p>“Vincent: <i>ayaw ko pong mag suspend kaya po sumusunod po ako sa utos dito. Saka po para sa akin naman po yun. Walang record po.</i>” (“I don't like to be suspended that's why I'm following their orders. I know it's also for me. No record.”)</p> <p>“Ron: <i>ano po, sumusunod po sa utos dito hindi po pweding makipag away ganun. Kasi hahaba po eh. Kaya nananahimik na lang po ako kahit minsan ano po parang nakakapikon.</i>” (“I follow the orders like not engaging in fights so as not to extend my stay here. Even when my patience is tested, I would just remain silent.”)</p>

Table 4 depicts the generated themes (7) based on the participants' experiences during the conduct of the modules. Reflective, Conscious, Composed, Compassionate, Grateful, Faithful, and Obedient.

During the modules, the participants were able to self-reflect by acknowledging the impact brought by the incident they were involved in. The study defines Reflection as how the participants understand their actions and consequences. Their experiences taught them a

life-changing moral, especially when they were admitted to the center, which they recognized as one of the most difficult situations they have been. Below are some of the statements of the participants about the said theme:

“Vincent: opo dad. Mahirap po dito yung buhay. Saka baka po ano sa jail na po ako mapunta hindi na dito kapag ano po, dad, naulit.”
 (“Yes, Dad. The life here is difficult. Then, I might go into the jail if I repeated the same action.”)

“Mario: Yung nagawa ko po. Hindi po ano sila ma punta sa ganito. E napakahirap po ng ganito lalo na po sa city jail.”
 (“With what I have done, I hope that they won’t be placed in this situation as because it is very difficult especially being in the city jail.”)

Being conscious is another theme that can be considered as something positive. In the study Conscious refers to being aware and sensible of their wrongdoings and how these may affect their social identity. Since the participants know how capable they are of doing negative behaviors, they were able to realize the possible consequences of their actions, giving them the idea of controlling their emotions and behaviors. Statements below support the said theme:

“Jeremy: Tska po kasi ano, parang pag napakita ko yun parang wala nang lalapit sa akin”
 (“I reveal that truth about me, nobody would come near me.”)

“Ron: Hmm. Ano po kasi sir. ahhh kasi po hindi ako makahalubilu dito kasi po ano nahihya ako sa kaso ko. kasi ano po ano eh, baka lumayo sila pag nalaman nila yung nagawa ko.”

(“Hmm, I cannot mingle with them for I am ashamed of my case. They would probably stay away from me, once they find out what I’ve done.”)

“Tolits: kinokontrol ko po kasi dito yung galit ko. hindi na po. Ayaw kuna pong bumalik dito. Hehe.”
 (“I am controlling my anger here because I don't like to be back here, hehe.”)

Upon realizing the significance of managing their emotions and feelings, the participants recognized that being composed is essential to avoid negative encounters or conflicts. This study's composed refers to the participants’ behavior, feelings, and expressions in dealing with negative emotions. Below are some of the verbatim statements of the participants:

“Vincent: Kasi po hangat kaya ko naman pong intindihin sila ganun po para din po umiwas na din po sa gulo dito po. Para hindi na po mapaaway.”

(“I would try to understand them so that I could avoid being into fight again.”)

“Mario: ahh yun nga po, ano po, na dapat hindi po nagpapadala kaagad sa ano po, sa away. Kasi tayo din po nakakaawa pagka ano po, nangyari yung may nasaktan kang iba.”

(“Ahh that is it one should not be hooked into a fight. Because it would be a pity having hurt someone.”)

“Jeremy: Ahh bali pag ano po galit ka ganyan, wag na pong patulan o ilabas po agada gad.ano nalang po lumayo nalang”
 (“When you are angry do not react impulsively. Just walk away.”)

The participants' replies are possible manifestations that they are becoming aware of the importance of controlling their anger and avoiding negative confrontations. More so, it is relatively different during their pre-interview, wherein some of them disclosed their difficulties in managing their anger that led to aggressive actions, which is supported by the responses and observations of their center personnel.

Despite participants’ detrimental past, they still have this goodness in them. While conducting the modules, the participants’ side of being Compassionate was tapped. The study refers to how the participants express their genuine concern to others. Such findings are essential since they may develop or lead to prosocial behaviors. This is true in the study of Leiberg, Kilmecki, and Singer (2011), wherein they found that even short-term compassion could increase prosocial behaviors. Below are some statements supporting the said theme:

Vincent: minsan po pag kailangan po nila ng tulong, kahit hindi na po sila hihingi ng tulong magkukusa na po ako. Kunyari po pag nagbubuhay po sila ng lamesa upuan ganyan”

(“Sometimes when they need help, I am showing my initiative in helping them eventhough they don't ask for it. Example, when they would carry table, chairs, and like.”)

“Ron: ahh binibigyan ko din po sila ng pagkain. Pag wala po ng makain yung sa mga labas nung nasa labas pa po ako ganun.”
 (“Ahh, when I was still out of the center, I would do the same, giving food to the hungry.”)

Studies have consistently supported the connection between compassion and empathy. Although empathy and compassion are not the same (Singer & Klimecki, 2014), they are still related. In an article by UVA Health Medical Center (2019), compassion can take it further. It’s feeling what the person is feeling, holding it, accepting it, and taking some action.

It’s interesting to discover that when an individual suffers a problem with his empathy, compassion can be used to heal it (Hoffman, 2013). Accordingly, empathy is vital in understanding other’s emotions; however, empathy has a downside when it comes to the suffering of others. Klimecki, Leiberg, Ricard, and Singer (2013) discovered that when an individual shares the suffering of others too much, negative emotions increase. In addition, their study has found that having compassion significantly increases positive emotions. Likewise, it positively increases resilience and approaches to stressful situations (Klimecki et al., 2013).

Part of module 2 (“Secret Heart”) is to invite another resident they are unfamiliar with and share their hidden feelings or thoughts. During the said module, participants were grateful, which refers to how the participants recognized the help they brought by sharing their thoughts and feelings with others. This was new to them, bearing in mind that their center personnel found them reserved and usually isolated themselves and tended to avoid socialization with others. Supporting the said theme, below are some of the participants’ statements:

“*Vincent: magaan po sa pakiramdam dad. kasi po nalalabas ko po yung tinatago ko po. Katulad nga po nung mga barkada ko*”
 (“It was a fulfilling feeling, Dad, because I have expressed what I have kept inside, just like with my peer group”.)

“*Jeremy: ahh opo, yung at least nasabi ko na po, medyo magaan po sa pakiramdam.*”

(“Ahh yes, at least I have expressed it already. I felt better.”)

“*Tolits: masaya po. Naibahagi ko po sa kanya.*”

(“I am happy. I was able to express it to him.”)

Participants saw the importance of faith in their spiritual beliefs. In the study, Faithful refers to the participants’ strong spiritual faith and uses it as a motivation to become a better individual. Their recognition of its importance helps them by leaning on their spiritual trust. Furthermore, participants see this theme as an instrument for changing the views and perceptions of others towards them using connectedness with and being close to the sacred (Waaizman, 2007).

There are a lot of studies and resources in the field of forensic psychology explaining the relationship between crime and spirituality (Bartol & Bartol, 2014). As such, Johnson and Jang's (2011) study found that the use of religion, belief, and spirituality is significant in reducing adolescent criminal behaviors. Furthermore, according to multiple studies (Allen & Lo, 2010; Chui, Cheng & Wong, 2013) have already cited that those religious adolescents commit fewer crimes than their non-religious peers. Below are some of the statements that support the said theme:

“*Ron: sa sarili po. Saka manalig lang po sa taas.. ahh kasi po yung diyos lang naman po yung ano, yung may Karapatan na humusga. Ganun po.*”

(“For me, to keep the faith for God for He is the only one who could judge us.”)

“*Tolits: hihikayatin ko po sila na ano, yung mag simba maniwala sa diyos para maiwas sa gulo. Para po ano hindi sila gumaya sa akin po ganun.*”

(“I would encourage them to go to church and have faith in God in order to avoid being involved in fight and for them not to be like me.”)

“*Jeremy: Gusto kong ipakita na may diyos ako.*

kahit gusto ko po kahit, yung magbago na po yung tingin nila sa akin.”

(“I would like to show that I have God and change the way other people see me.”)

Lastly, participants’ recognized that the rules of the center ground them. This entails them showing obedience since it may lead to consequences such as suspension or possible corrective behavioral interventions if specific rules or regulations are disobeyed. In the present study, Obedient refers to the characteristics of the participants to be a good follower. Such behavior is considered one of the possible contributing factors that could help these juveniles change their lives for the better, which was also evident during the first phase of the data collection. Observing the rules and regulations of the center is a way of holding them accountable for their behaviors (Mackin, Lucas, Lambarth, Herrera, Walter, Carey & Finigian, 2010).

Post-Assessment Phase: Administration of Questionnaires and Interviews after the conduct of the Creative Therapy Modules

Table 5. Participants level of Aggression after the conduct of the Modules

Verbal Interpretation	Physical Aggression				Verbal Aggression				Anger				Hostility				Overall Aggression			
	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD	f	%	Mean	SD
High (3.34 – Above)	0	0.0			0	0.00			0	0.00			0	0.00			0	0.00		
Average (1.67 – 3.33)	6	100	2.35	0.78	6	100		0.25	5	83.34	2.26	0.60	6	100	2.21	0.56	6	100	2.31	0.13
Low (1.66 – Below)	0	0.0			0	0.00	2.44		1	16.66			0	0.00			0	0.00		

Results are positive manifestations that the participants can manage their anger and emotions. Concurrent with this end product, the participants' experiences are closely related to these changes, such as being composed when facing provocative situations and conscious

about their actions by avoiding conflict and using positive confrontation when facing uneasy situations. In addition, their faith or spiritual belief could have influenced such a decrease in aggressive tendencies.

Supporting the said results, the center personnel were vocal in stating some facts based on their observations of these juveniles with aggressive behaviors. Accordingly, participants were seen as having a sense of control over their emotions and behavior. They become aware of how important managing anger is and how to confront situations positively. They become more composed, describing the participants' behavior, feelings, and expressions as under control. According to their center personnel:

“RSW: Hindi ko siya nakitaan ng katapangan ng mukha, yung parang sinisisi niya kami”
 (“I did not see any hostility in his face, instead of blaming us.”)

“HP: Tapos kwan ano yung mapag timpi siya, nag susumbong agad pag may problema sa loob”
 (“He is in control of his emotions and when there are problems he would just report it to us.”)

“PCW: And notable changes niyan sir na nakita ko e mapagtimpi ngayon, kasi yun nga madalas yan mabuyo eh. pero nag aano siya kung бага kumakabig siya ngayon, last time kasi na meet ko yan tapos nasabi saken nga na my nag nakaw daw ng notebook niya sa locker, usually kasi yan sir mabigat kamay. Pero nag sumbong lang siya hindi nag wala katulad dati”
 (“And a notable change from him Sir is his temperance, because he was often prompted. Now, he can control his emotions. Just like when I spent time with him, he mentioned that somebody took his notebook. Instead of resorting to fistfight, he just informed me about it.”)

Such results are directly related to the study of Sarpoulaki and Kolahi (2016). Accordingly, their results indicated that play therapy caused a dramatic drop in violence in all three components of physical, verbal, and relational in children. This result is also consistent with the previous literature cited that play therapy is an effective therapeutic intervention for children with a high level of aggressive tendencies and violent behaviors (Alavinezhad et al., 2014; Hall et al. 2002; Sarpoulaki & Kolahi, 2016).

Most participants gained their realizations through reflection and being conscious of their actions to avoid conflict and later aggressive tendencies. With these findings, Hub (2013) discovered that using play therapy as an intervention provides insight to deal with inner conflicts and other corrective emotional experiences vital in an individual's healing process. Likewise, the study of Bratton and Ray (2000) and Padilla and Pierson (2015) found that play-based interventions could help people process emotional issues and later develop a healthier social life. Below are some of the participants' statements which support the said results:

Tolits: kinokontrol ko po kasi dito yung galit ko. hindi na po. Ayaw kuna pong bumalik dito. Hehe.”
 (“I am controlling my anger here because I don't like to be back here, hehe.”)

“Vincent: Kasi po hangat kaya ko naman pong intindihin sila ganun po para din po umiwas na din po sa gulo dito po. Para hindi na po mapaaway.”
 (“I would try to understand them so that I could avoid being into fight again.”)

“Jeremy: Ahh bali pag ano po galit ka ganyan, wag na pong patulan o ilabas po agada gad.ano nalang po lumayo nalang”
 (“When you are angry do not react impulsively. Just walk away.”)

Table 6: Participants level of Empathy after the conduct of the Modules

Verbal Interpretation	f	%	Mean	SD
High (15 – Above)	6	100	20.67	2.06
Low (14 – Below)	0	0.00		

n=6

Table 6 shows the result of the participants' level of empathy after the conduct of the modules. There are changes in the said construct since they scored high compared to the low level before the start of the modules.

This development was attributed to their behaviors during and after the modules. Based on their consolidated responses, participants acknowledged their past wrongdoings utilizing reflecting. Such realization helped the participants become more aware and conscious in their actions that may prevent them from engaging in aggressive behaviors. In addition, they became more sensible about their actions and how they may affect their social image or identity. Aside from the abovementioned observations, participants were also able to show genuine concern to others and be more compassionate in helping their co-residents who are in need whether material or emotional aspect. According to one of the participants:

“Joselito: pagka my problema po yung kaibigan po, handa ko po silang pakingan. Basta po e kaya ko po naman e tutulong naman po ako”
 (“When my friends have a problem, I'm willing to listen. As long as I can, I am really willing to help.”)

Supporting the said changes, center personnel found the participants to be more approachable and show concern by helping others in their tasks particularly in household chores. Here are some of the verbatim statements of the center personnel:

“RSW: ah yung madalas kong nakikita diyana na matulungin ngayon yung hawak ko si Tolits and Ron. Bali madalas sila active ngayon

sa task nila dito tapos tumutulong pag may nakikita sila na nag bubuhat ganun”

(“The usual residents who help out in the center are Tolits and Ron. They are active in assisting others and in their tasks)

“HP: Ahh si kwan sir ngayon si Jeremy mas naging malapit sa iba. compared before diba na un nga medyo ilag. Ngayon makikita mo nag ooffer ng tulong yan sa mga bata dito pati sa amin lalo na sa office.

(“Jeremy who has been observed to be aloof is now very close to others and even offers help to those residents who are in need, specially to us and in the office”)

Previous studies (Feshbach & Feshbach, 1969; Mehrabian & Epstein, 2006) carried out among children and adults have found a consistent inverse relationship between empathy and aggression. This is related to the present study since the participants obtained a high level of empathy and an average level regarding aggression.

According to Spellings (2007), there is evidence that promoting and developing empathy-related skills are vital in reducing aggressive behaviors. Such evidence was also supported by past (Miller & de Haar, 1997) and even recent studies that highly empathic children are less likely to be affected by adverse experiences when exposed to strong negative emotions of others, and they are thereby disposed to act more prosocially (Blair, 2018).

Furthermore, empathy is recognized as a driver of prosocial behavior (Decety et al. 2015), which is evident in this study since the participants’ level of empathy scored high that permits them to perform favorable acts and behaviors, such as helping others and dismissing a negative feeling when faced by provocative situations.

Table 7: Participants level of Prosocial Behavior after the conduct of the Modules

Verbal Interpretation	f	%	Mean	SD
High (4.68 – Above)	6	100	6.03	0.45
Average (2.34 – 4.67)	0	0.00		
Low (2.33 - Below)	0	0.00		

n=6

Table 7 reflects the results of the participants after the conduct of the modules about prosocial behavior. Like empathy, the participants’ scores on the said construct yielded a high level.

Such results can be attributed to their behavior of being obedient to the rules and regulations of the center, sharing positive spiritual insights to strengthen their faith, and, more so, being compassionate in sharing or helping others who are in need since prosocial behavior is considered an action intended to help others (University of Missouri-Columbia, 2014). Individuals act prosocially when they detect cues or signals suggesting independence from others (Matsumoto et al. 2016), similar to what the participants are currently experiencing.

Aside from the said behaviors, center personnel observed some participants' behaviours after the modules' conduct. Participants were perceived to be more sociable, indicating that they increased their ability to socialize effectively and avoid isolating themselves. Studies have shown a positive connection between sociability and prosocial behavior. The study of Lam (2012) found that individuals who involve themselves in interpersonal transactions can increase their tendency to be prosocial. Likewise, according to Knafo-Noam and Markovitch (2015), prosocial behavior is related positively to sociability and activity involvement. Below are the verbatim statements of the center personnel with this claim:

“HP: involve siya sa mga ano, sa mga activity namin dito sa center. Kasi dati ano yan. Taong kwarto yan sir. mas active siya. ngayon pupunta sa siya akin, sa gardening sumasali siya. mas engaged siya”

(“From a person who chooses to stay in his room, he now participates in the activities and now more active, like in being with me in the garden area.”)

“HP: kasi one-time sa likod e naghuhukay kasi ang mga yan sa likod para sa basura namin, tapos naririnig ko na parang nag tatawanan sila sa likod kasama nung iba. bihira ko lang makita yang ganyan kasi sir eh. Dati kasi kahit isama mo yan sa iba walang imik yan.”

(“Because one time at the backyard they are digging for our trash, then I heard like they were laughing at the back with others. I seldom see that kind of event, Sir. Before, even when you keep him in the company of others he would not talk.”)

“RSW: Pero yung na observe ko sakanya ngayon is ano, nasa common place siya yung may TV diyan near covered court. Hindi ko naman siya madalas nakikita dati dun eh, saka kita mo nakikipag tawanan siya ngayon unlike before nakay mam Deth lang yan sa kusina.”

(“What I have observed is that he stays at the TV area near the covered court and enjoys being with others, not only with Ma’am Deth. I do not usually see him like this.”)

“PCW: Kunyari nalang sir si ano Ron, pa mysterious yan before, ngayon kita ko siya madalas sa common area, aba nanunuod kasama ng iba. yung alam mong nakikijoin na siya kasi dati pag ano after exercise sa umaga pasok agad kwarto yan. Ngayon, tambay. Hehe”

(“Just for instance, Ron acts mysteriously before and usually goes back to the room after exercise. But now, I frequently see him in the common area. He watches TV together with the others. Hanging out. Hehe”)

Several studies, such as Krahe and Möller (2011) and Eivers, Brendgen, Vitaro and Borge (2012), have found a negative correlation between prosocial behavior and aggression. These studies are relatively connected to this since participants obtained a high level of prosocial behavior and average aggression.

Figure 2: Mean score distribution before and after the Therapy

Figure 2 reflects the participants' mean scores before and after the conduct of creative therapy modules using a line graph. Looking at the trajectory of scores, it can be said that there are changes in their behaviors. Aggression yielded a mean of 4.07 before the conduct of the modules but later decreased after the conduct of the modules, having a score of 2.31. Meanwhile, empathy scored low (13) before the conduct of the modules. However, after the intervention, it yielded a high level, corresponding to a score of 20.67. Lastly, though prosocial behavior was already noted positively (4.23) before the conduct of the modules, still, there is an increase in the scores (6.03) after the conduct of the modules.

Table 8: Difference between Pre-Test and Post-Test scores of the participants on the following behaviors

Behaviors	t	df	Sig
Aggression			
Physical Aggression (Pre-Post)	6.735	5	.001
Verbal Aggression (Pre-Post)	18.508	5	.000
Anger (Pre-Post)	11.829	5	.000
Hostility (Pre-Post)	13.484	5	.000
Overall Aggression (Pre-Post)	11.284	5	.000
Empathy			
Empathy (Pre-Post)	-7.064	5	.001
Prosocial Behavior			
Prosocial (Pre-Post)	-5.234	5	.003

Sig. Level < 0.05

Table 8 answers the last research question: is there a significant difference between the participants' pre and post-test scores on the said behaviors? It is evident, based on the results, that all the behaviors yielded a significant difference (Aggression .000 < 0.05; Empathy .001 < 0.05; Prosocial Behavior .003 < 0.05) which, in this study, rejects the null hypothesis.

Results can be supported by multiple data sources from their center personnel and empirical results from related studies and literature.

Having mentioned this, aggression can be supported by the qualitative responses of the participants as well as the observations of their center personnel. Particular themes that emerged contribute to these dramatic changes of behavior are composed, conscious, obedient and self-reflection. Their experiences taught them how to control their anger and the consequences of their actions, which prompted them not to act violently.

Also, the center's diversion program greatly impacted these juveniles, helping them divert their attention more productively. More so, the positive effect of the modules was identified as one of the main reasons for this behavioral development. The lessons they learned from the modules were evident since some participants could apply them provocatively.

Supporting the impact of creative therapy modules in this study, several pieces of literature (Alavinezhad et al., 2014; Hall et al., 2002; Sarpoulaki & Kolahi, 2016) have found that using play therapy in treating children with aggressive tendencies and violent behaviors decrease such negative behaviors.

On the other hand, it was found that there is a significant difference between the pre-and post-evaluation of the participants' level of empathy (.001 < 0.05). Such a result can be attributed to their acknowledgment of their past behaviors. Given the said realizations, the participants became more aware and sensible with their actions, which helped them avoid conflict, which led me to their ability to help others and show genuine concern for those in need. This behavior will help decrease an individual's aggressive tendencies (Spellings,

2007). These juveniles are starting to realize the importance of showing empathy to others, which could lead to a more positive outcome (Blair, 2018; Miller & de Haar, 1997).

Lastly, the results also yielded a significant difference in prosocial behavior (.003<0.05). Since empathy is directly related to prosocial behavior (Decety et al., 2015), participants' compassionate behaviour in helping others could lead to these prosocial acts. Likewise, these juveniles were mandated by cues to perform positive behavior, such as completing their daily routine and following the set of rules of the center. These observations are parallel to Matsumoto, et al., (2016) study that explains the idea of acting prosocially when individuals detect signals or cues suggesting independence from others.

Multiple studies have found an inverse connection between aggression and prosocial behavior (Eivers et al., 2012; Krahé & Möller, 2011). These findings are related to the results of this study since the participants were assessed to have a high level of prosocial behavior and average when it comes to aggression after the conduct of the modules.

The positive behavioral changes were attributed to the modules that were provided to them. center personnel are satisfied since the needs of the participants were met through the modules. In addition, the said modules positively affected participants' behavior in the center and perception in life.

Studies attested that creative therapy, specifically play-based intervention, has a significant impact towards children who manifest aggressive tendencies. It was discovered in numerous studies (Alavinezhad et al., 2014; Hall et al., 2002; Sarpoulaki & Kolahi, 2016) that conducting such therapy can dramatically decrease the level of aggression and violent behaviors among children. Even in a recent study (Davis & Bailey, 2019), it was found that play-based interventions have been shown to contribute to reducing a constellation of symptoms related to aggression.

Below are some of the statements of center personnel directed towards this premise:

“HP: yung katulad nung mga therapies nyo, yun talagang nakaka tulong sa kanila yun”
 (“Just like your therapies, they really help them.”)

“RSW: Tapos sir yung ano, yung therapy nyo, yung intervention. Kasi nakita ko talaga na very open sila. Tapos mas na cocontrol nila yung inis nila”
 (“Then Sir, the therapy and type of interventions you give made them be open about their feelings and at the same time be in control of their emotions.”)

“RSW: ahh ito sir hindi sa ano ha yung tinataas ko yung upuan mo, pero I think una yung sayo sir. sabi ko mga madaming factors. Kasi bakit ko nasabi, mas naiintidihan kasi nila yung sarili nila ngayon lalo na si Vince. Mas naiintidihan niya yung situation niya na kinakaharap ngayon. Unlike dati”
 (“It is not that I am trying to flatter you, but your therapy has positively affected the children. This is because they are now more aware of who they are, especially Vince. He now has a clearer perception of his situation.”)

Aside from the center personnel statement, one of the participants express his positive observation and help brought by the modules. He said verbatim:

“Mario: ser nakakatulong po yung ganito, yung kwan po, kasi wala po talaga akong napag sasabihan ng mga ganito, yung mga nagagawa ko dito ser”
 (“Sir this is a big help, because there's no body I am sharing what I've been through here”)

Supporting the positive impact of the modules, multiple studies are addressing the importance of interventions and interventions that are effective for these types of juveniles. A late research conducted by Howell (1995), as cited by Vries and Liem (2011), may support the importance of providing the participants' systematic interventions since Howell's findings shed light on the impact of decreasing the chances of recidivism of JHOs by providing them treatments like individual counseling and life skills development.

According to the Texas Youth Commission (2002), JHOs who underwent programs and interventions had significant changes in their behavior and personality, such as being less hostile and aggressive, assuming more responsibility, and having more empathy for their victims during program involvement.

Talking approaches in addressing the violent behaviors of youth this can be categorized into two according to Christle and Nelson (2006); first is reactive approaches, which consist of interventions that involve treatment of existing problems after the fact, similar to the creative therapy modules which were provided to the participants, while second is the proactive strategies which address potential risks and attempt to prevent problems from becoming manifest.

Related to the abovementioned approaches, past studies (Greenberg, Domitrovich & Bumbarger, 1999; Guetzloe, 2000) brought up some related prevention approaches. One of which is called secondary prevention, wherein the strategies are applied through targeted interventions and include efforts geared to specific problems of individuals. This type of intervention is somehow anchored to the creative therapy modules, which target particular behaviors such as aggression, empathy and prosocial behavior.

Although intervention efforts traditionally have focused on treatment after the fact (Christle & Nelson, 2006), it is undeniable that decades of research (Hawkins, Herrenkohl, Farrington, Brewer, Catalon, Harachi, & Cothorn, 2000; Synder, 2000), suggest that prevention is the most effective strategy available for reducing violent behaviors among youth.

Treatment or intervention for these juveniles is a vital ingredient to prevent them from recidivism tendencies. In the study conducted by Khachatryan (2015) it shows that juvenile homicide offenders who were provided with interventions and treated were less likely to be arrested than those who were untreated. Consistent with the previous studies and reports (Heide, 2013; Texas Youth Commission, 2010), they found that youth who completed the program were less likely to be re-incarcerated compared to youths who did not participate. Likewise, treated juveniles were also less likely to be rearrested for a violent or any offense than their untreated counterparts.

Since creative therapy modules target the participants' behaviour, some studies validate the effectiveness of behavioral-related interventions. Previous studies found that interventions related to behavioral, cognitive-behavioral, skills-oriented or life skills, and family interventions were the most successful treatment strategies for juvenile offenders (Palmer, 2002). Another late study (Lipse, Wilson & Cothorn, 2002), stipulated some of the most effective approach or treatment programs for juvenile homicide offenders. These contain individual counseling, interpersonal skills, and behavioral interventions.

Multiple studies have testified that using creative therapy such as play therapy is effective and efficient in reducing aggressive tendencies (Sarpoulaki & Kolahi, 2016), providing them insights and drawing realization about their inner conflict (Hub, 2013) and promoting positive social skills (Bratton & Ray, 2000; Padilla & Pierson, 2015).

Aside from the creative therapy modules, the center's diversion program was also a factor that led to these behavioral changes and positively diverted the attention of these juveniles. Such a program was incorporated into the daily routine of the participants. In addition, following the rules the center imposed to modify and guide the participants' behavior is also considered vital in changing their behaviors. These helped them avoid provocative situations that may result in conflict. Some of the participants, along with the center personnel, their testaments directed to these rules:

“Joselito: dito hindi po. Kasi po ano po narerecord nga po. Tas suspended po”
 (“...Here sir, no. Because it will be recorded. Then you'll be suspended.”)

“Ron: ano po, sumusunod po sa utos dito hindi po pwedng makipag away ganun. Kasi hahaba po eh. Kaya nananahimik nlang po ako kahit minsan ano po parang nakaka pikon.”
 (“It's that, I follow orders around here for I cannot be involved in a brawl. My (sentence) will be prolonged. So, I just keep quiet even if sometimes it annoys me.”)

“RSW: ahh isa din sakanila sir na nakatulong, is yung activity nila na sa schooling nila ngayon. Siguru nagkaroon sila ng abalihin.”
 (“Ahh, their school work made them occupied in a good way.”)

“HP: siguro dito sa center, kasi ang bilin ko lagi sa kanila e mga mabubuting bagay yung mapapakita o mapupulot sa ibang kapwa hindi yung mga masasma”
 (“...maybe here in the center, because what I advise to them is always good deeds or be a good influence”)

“RSW: tapos siguru yung ano din pag momonitor ng house parent at yung dito din sa daily routine nila sir. more on house hold”
 (“Then, maybe also with the monitoring of the house parent and their daily routine here, it is more on house hold chores.”)

The importance of facilities in helping these juveniles is evident in many studies. According to Piquero and Steinberg (2010), as cited by DeLisi, Hochstetler, Johnson, Caudill, and Marquart, (2011), facilities where juveniles can be confined were viewed positively since it enhances community safety by incapacitating violent young offenders, and it holds them accountable for their offenses. In addition, it incentivises these children to respond and participate in different programs and interventions provided by the center, which facilitates their interest. Likewise, past research (Dembo, Wareham, Schmeidler & Chirikos, 2005) found that diversion programs have shown positive results on the behavior of juveniles. On the other hand, the diversion program of the center is incorporated into the participants' daily routine, such as doing household chores, spiritual enhancement, livelihood activities and other life skills programs. Thus, it was one of the factors for some behavioral reforms in the participants.

Institutionalized facilities or programs like interpersonal skills, teaching family homes, behavioral programs, community residential activities, and multiple services were found effective (Heide, 2003). Moreover, diversion programs have numerous benefits, such as reducing involvement in delinquent acts and maintaining youth connectedness and engagement in the community by keeping them in their environment (Youth.Org, 2019).

But despite the received help from the modules and the centre's diversion program, center personnel still recognized what was lacking in helping these juveniles. Based on their statements, these juveniles are deprived of programs that address their specific needs and concerns. There were particular reasons; specifically, the lack of trained and qualified professionals to administer psychological interventions like counseling, was recorded. Some of the statements of the center personnel explicitly stressed this concern:

“HP: Lalo na pag ganun kaso yung ginawa nila. Wala naman kasi talaga akong nakikita na therapy o kaya yung sir, yung katulad nung ginagawa niyo na ano may ganun, wala kasi talaga.”

(“Especially if the type of crime they have committed is severe, I don’t really see any therapy Sir, just like what you’re doing Sir, there is nothing really.”)

“HP: Pag kaano lang po pag may bisita o OJT. Pero yung regular ala man sir eh. Puro small talks lang ganun”

(“When there’s a visitor or OJT’s but someone regular, there’s none. It’s pure small talks, like that.”)

“HP: kasi sir makikita mo talaga dito sa amin ha, small talks lang talaga kaya namin, kung baga father and mother figure lang. e syempre iba pa din yung mga my basis talaga katulad niyang ginagawa niyo sir. kaya sa mapadalas kayo dito. hehe.”

(“Because Sir you can really notice here with us, we can only do small talks, it was just like a father and mother figure. Ofcourse having a basis is still different, just like what you’re doing Sir. That’s why I hope you often visit here. Hehe”)

“PCW: Yun yung isa sa pinaka kwan ko, na sana kung meron pong kagaya niyo na tututok talaga, malaki talaga yung potential nung mga bata na mag bago sir. Kung baga kulang lang talaga sa proseso yung mga bata”

(“I really hope that there would be someone who could prioritize these children, because there is a great potential for them to get better. It is as if they are in need of this kind of process (counseling).”)

Their diversion program focuses on life skills and livelihood activities that overshadow counseling and other psychological interventions. Even before, literature expressed the need to provide a more holistic approach to helping youth who committed homicide (Myers, 1992). In treating these juveniles, interventions should be focused on psychotherapy and the need for institutional placement.

Late studies made some clarifications about proper and effective interventions. These studies found that some institutions use interventions not based on established therapeutic principles or empirically documented success (Benedek et al. 1989; Tate et al. 1995).

With limited access to psychological intervention, JHOs face several problems, especially in the aspect of interventions. The potential danger that these juveniles pose is concerns related to the most appropriate treatment of such deep-end offenders (Trulson & Caudill, 2017)

One of the center’s struggles is its lack of qualified professionals to facilitate psychological interventions. The problem shows no licensed psychologists or counselors in the center. The chances of providing these juveniles with a mental health program before they return to society are vague. This is true in the study of Heide (2003), wherein even though juvenile homicide offenders will be released into society, few were fortunate enough to receive the type of mental health treatment following the homicide. Similar results were found in a local study (Cabildo & Reysio-Cruz, 2016) that their emotional and mental health conditions are given less attention since there is unfitness of interventions caused by outnumbered qualified professionals. Furthermore, scrutinizing the program and models of service delivery and the effectiveness of rehabilitation programs is needed (Day, Howells & Rickwood, 2004).

After a thorough investigation of the effects of creative therapy on six (6) JHOs’ aggressive tendencies, as well as their ability to empathize and show prosocial acts and behaviors, using a mixed method specifically embedded concurrent experimental design, it can be recognized that there is a positive development and changes on the said behaviors before and after receiving the therapy. Statistically speaking, scores before the conduct of the modules were evaluated as high in terms of aggression. The process observers validated this based on their observations of the participants. Issues like picking fights, verbal arguments, and other aggressive related behaviors were seen from the participants even while undergoing their rehabilitation program. Such behaviors were already present before committing the case and during their admission to the center. This is related to their tendency to become hotheaded – making them less empathic to others. Nevertheless, due to the instruction set by the center, participants were considered obedient and cooperative in any task given to them.

During the conduct of the therapy, experiences brought by the modules were found positive. This indicates that the participants could process their thoughts concerning their aggressive tendencies and other related behaviors. Seven (7) themes emerged based on their experiences throughout the therapy. They could reflect and understand the consequences of their actions and became conscious and aware of their wrongdoings and how they affect their social identity. In addition, participants dealt positively with their behaviors – causing them to be more composed without causing any conflict. Being compassionate or their ability to help others was also tapped during the therapy. These commendable changes created a sense of gratitude to the participants for sharing their feelings with others. It did manifest during the therapy that the participants had established their spiritual faith and used it as their motivation to help themselves. Lastly, participants recognize the influenced of the center on their behaviors. Since they were grounded by the rules and regulations of the center, the participants were more obedient to the center's mandate.

The participants’ scores under aggression, empathy, and prosocial behavior improved after the therapy was conducted. They scored average on aggression, which is a good manifestation that they are starting to regulate and manage their anger and other related emotions. Such results are directly related to the participants' experiences during therapy like being composed when confronted by provocative situations and conscious about their actions. This was certified by the process observers, who have witnessed the participants having a sense of control of their emotions and behavior and are aware of the importance of managing anger and confronting situations positively.

Both empathy and prosocial behavior scored high after the therapy. This notable development was attributed to their behaviors during and after the creative therapy modules. Some of these are how the participants reflect and acknowledge their previous actions and become more sensible about their behaviors and how they affect themselves. Such realizations helped these participants prevent further emotional outbursts that led to aggressive acts and behaviors. Furthermore, participants also engaged themselves more often in helping inside the center and showed compassion and genuine concern towards others. These positive changes in their behaviors were also noted by the process observers, who found the participants more approachable than previous observations before the conduct of therapy. More so, after the therapy, participants were perceived as more sociable – enhancing their interpersonal skills and avoiding isolating themselves.

This development and differences in terms of the behaviors before and after the conduct of the therapy were found to be statistically significant. Results indicate that creative therapy modules significantly impact aggression, empathy and prosocial behaviors. Themes related to reduced aggression include composed, conscious, obedient, and self-reflection. Meanwhile, process observers cited the modules as one of the main reasons the said behaviors improved and achieved such development.

Significant differences were also noted in empathy, wherein the participant's behavior was directly attributed to their acknowledgment of their past behaviors and able to become aware of their actions and behaviors to avoid further conflict. Likewise, prosocial behavior was found to be statistically significant difference before and after the therapy. This development was seen and noted by the process observers; the participants are more inclined to help others since most of them acknowledge their mistakes and extend help to others.

Conclusion

After thoroughly analyzing the results and findings of the study, it has been concluded that these juveniles possessed a high level of aggression and a low to an average level of empathy and prosocial behaviors during the pre-assessment part of the study. The process observers observed behaviors related to aggressive tendencies while undergoing their rehabilitation program. Performing violent acts and behaviors before the conduct of the therapy makes them less empathic. More so, grounded by rules set by the center, most of the juveniles displayed and were encouraged to perform prosocial acts and behaviors by following the rules and regulations of the center.

Themes emerged (7) based on the participants' experiences during the conduct of therapy. Most of the experiences focused on reducing aggressive tendencies, such as being conscious of their actions and behaviors, and some realizations that taught them life-changing experiences and used them to avoid conflict. Such reflections helped them to become more composed, which is vital in preventing negative and unhealthy confrontations that may result in conflict. Also, during the therapy, participants acknowledged the importance of confiding with others, which made them grateful. The findings are new since, before the therapy, process observers saw these juveniles as reserved and tended to avoid socialization. In addition, having strong faith was one of their driving forces to become a better version of themselves despite their current social status. More so, seeing the importance of following the rules and regulations of the center makes them more obedient, which can be used as one of the tools to improve their lives.

Positive changes occurred after the therapy, including lowering aggressive tendencies and a high level of empathy and prosocial behavior. Multiple sources could validate this, including the participants' experiences during the therapy, as well as the observations of the process observers. The average level of aggression can be attributed to their experiences during therapy, such as being composed and conscious about their actions and signaling them to avoid conflict. Process observers included their share in this development when they perceived these juveniles as people who had realizations of their past behaviors and became aware and mindful of their actions to avoid provocative situations. Thus, increased empathic concern to others and prosocial behaviors can be attributed to their experiences as being compassionate in helping others and showing genuine concern towards other residents. Meanwhile, process observers saw these juveniles enhanced their interpersonal skills. They were apparent to be more sociable compared to before.

Lastly, there is a significant difference between the pre-and post-test assessments on aggression, empathy, and prosocial behavior. It can be said that creative therapy modules made a substantial impact on these juveniles' behaviors. This was attested by the process observers, who acknowledged the therapy's vital contribution in helping these juveniles improve the said behaviors. In addition, the center's diversion program cannot be discounted as a contributing factor in the participants' behavioral changes. However, the center still struggles to provide tailored fit interventions that address their distinct needs since one of the concerns the process observers raise is the lack of competent professionals in developing and facilitating psychological-related interventions like counseling.

Based on the results and findings of the study, the following recommendations were made: The center's program must be modified to achieve a genuinely holistic approach that is still tailor-fitted to the CICLs' status since the treatment is solely focused on life skills (e.g. household chores, livelihood programs, etc.). In this light, a counseling program is an inevitable need to modify and cultivate the positive behavior of these youths. Considering the accuracy of skills required in the profession and the classification of cases, qualified counselors can solely supervise and execute such a program. Thus, the center must reiterate to the national government the urgent need for licensed professionals, like counselors or psychologists, who are equipped to facilitate psychological interventions. In the absence of a licensed professional in the center, adapting the creative therapy modules would supplement the center's existing activities in fulfillment of the holistic approach.

The Department of Social Welfare and Development should prioritize the conduct of training for center personnel on how to properly

handle and manage the behaviors of CICLthe Likewise, equipping the personnel and houseparents with procedures in facilitating activities and interventions to aid and address behavioral issues and concerns appropriately.

Counselor educators could integrate the importance of developing creative therapy modules to address different behavioral concerns of their clients and other special populations in their lessons. Preventive approaches or programs on the school level must be developed and introduced to learners and parents to raise awareness and make preventive measures for youngsters involved in such incidents.

For future researchers, the number of participants must be increased to strengthen the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, the study must be conducted in a longitudinal approach with a controlled and experimental group to ensure the efficiency of the modules. Lastly, creative therapy modules must be polished and reviewed by looking into their effect and feedback from the participants, wherein they may include supplementary behaviors and modules in line with the status of these juveniles.

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